

DIDACTIC PROPOSAL IN BILINGUAL PHYSICAL EDUCATION ON CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING (CLIL) TEAM SPORTSⁱ

Santiago García-Calvo Rojoⁱⁱ

Universidad de Castilla La Mancha,
España

Abstract:

This article puts forward a didactic proposal of content and language integrated learning in Bilingual Physical Education subject. In the proposal are merged motor skills and English as a second language (L2). Therefore, the aim is the learning of a second language using the contents of Physical education matter. Therefore, the conceptual frame is known as the 4Cs framework (content, cognition, communication and culture). The designed and developed tasks of Physical education are related to motor, cognitive and communicative skills. The didactic proposal is aimed at students of 6th grade of Primary Education and the curriculum design transforms theory into practice in the academic year 2016-2017. Thanks to the educative praxis, the curriculum development has been revised in accordance with current legislation. The implementation of the proposal has allowed us to adjust for conclusions and improve the learning and teaching process.

Keywords: didactic proposal, primary education, bilingual physical education, second language acquisition, CLIL

Resumen:

El artículo plantea una propuesta didáctica de aprendizaje integrado de contenido y lengua en el área de Educación Física bilingüe. En ella se fusionan las habilidades motrices con la enseñanza del inglés como lengua extranjera (L2). Por tanto, el objetivo es el aprendizaje de una segunda lengua a través de los contenidos del área de educación física. Para ello, se parte del marco conceptual conocido como las 4Cs (contenido, cognición, comunicación y cultura). Las tareas diseñadas y desarrolladas de educación física guardan relación con habilidades motrices, cognitivas y comunicativas. La propuesta didáctica va destinada a 6^o curso de Educación Primaria y parte de un

ⁱ PROPUESTA DIDÁCTICA EN EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA BILINGÜE DE APRENDIZAJE INTEGRADO DE CONTENIDO Y LENGUA (AICLE). DEPORTES DE EQUIPO

ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email sposantgarcia@gmail.com

diseño curricular puesto en práctica en el curso escolar 2016-2017. Este diseño y desarrollo curricular, gracias a la práctica educativa, ha sido revisado y adaptado a la legislación vigente. Esto nos ha permitido realizar ajustes posteriores y obtener conclusiones para mejorar el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje.

Palabras clave: propuesta didáctica, educación primaria, educación física bilingüe, adquisición de una segunda lengua, AICLE

1. Introduction

First of all, it is crucial to understand that Physical Education in the 21st century is not only to teach sports or motor skills. PE has to be used to teach values, life skills, physical competences, problems solving and communicative skills. Therefore, it presented a proposal of content-integrated learning.

This is an innovative didactic approach based on the legal framework of reference established for this purpose by the Educational and Science Ministry and the Educational Counsel of Castilla-La Mancha. National Organic Law in education (LOE 2/2006); National Organic Law for improving quality of education (LOMCE 8/2013); Decree 54/2014, establishes Primary Education curriculum and Decree 7/2014, regulates multilingualism in Castilla- La Mancha.

The Didactic Unit designed is an original proposal which is part of a long term Syllabus. In both, content of a subject matter (Physical Education) and English language are integrated. The didactic unit aims at 6th grade of Primary Education and it based on another didactic approach (García-Calvo, 2015). This has been enriched and updated legislatively for academic year 2016-2017. Therefore, it shows a session's template that explains in-depth how to teach PE in CLIL using the medium of English language.

The curriculum design allows us to plan rationally a set of activities based on previous objectives. Contreras (1998) states that planning enable us to control several variables, so we are transforming an idea into an action. On the other hand, when we put into practice a motor skill designed, we are developing the contents and the objectives we want.

Physical Education has three domains of learning: affective, cognitive and psychomotor. The psychomotor domain has a backbone and two links: body and movement. Bilingual Physical Education includes all domains and different types of input to CLIL students are exposed. Therefore, we have to use two links and a second language (English) as a conductive thread.

The dual focus and communicative aspects will involve changes in the way of teaching. The subject matter contents, the teaching of English skills and thinking skills are blended. (Gonzalez-Villora et al., 2013) states that the curriculum is going to suffer a change of meaning. The contents really do not change, but the language will change (L1-L2). The activities are not going to be so much different, but these must be

integrated. The methodology is going to suffer variations. The objectives and assessment will have two profiles: physical and linguistic.

CLIL in PE is holistic approach and learning in CLIL PE occurring in several levels. We have to bear in mind linguistic, metalinguistic, cognitive, affective and motor components. *“This means not considering two subjects, but a single”* (García-Calvo, 2015). Halbach (2008) suggest that *“the children understand the knowledge as whole and for them it is not natural to separate what they learn into two blocks or subjects”*.

Teaching a non-linguistic discipline involves an incredible effort. Therefore, the coordination of all staff is essential when we teach PE in CLIL. The effort will be rewarded if the results improve the educational quality (Coral and Lleixá, 2013).

2. Didactic Proposal

Sánchez (2002), states that the syllabus is a dynamic, open, flexible and realistic document and there is room for improvement. Escamilla (1992) defines the Didactic Unit as the way to plan the learning and teaching process around the contents and objectives.

The constructivism approach and integrated learning are related. Villanueva y Navarro (1997) considers that vehicular language linked to communicative skills improves communication.

Coyle, Hood and Marsh (2010) provide a planning map for CLIL using the 4Cs framework and the tool kit. They write that CLIL methodology develops linguistic skills and cognitive flexibility. The 4Cs framework has four major components which can be synthesized in: Content, Cognition, Culture and Communication. Content is the thematic learning as the vocabulary of a non-linguistic discipline; Cognition is understanding and cognitive skills related to Bloom’s taxonomy; Culture is to foster international understanding and the fruit of the relationship with other cultures and Communication is language learning (grammatical concepts) and language using (communication). The 4Cs are integrated to develop motor, communicative, individual, social and cognitive skills (Coral and Lleixa, 2013).

“Connecting the 4Cs into an integrated whole is fundamental to planning” (Coyle et al., 2010). Communicative aspect has three useful parts for planning, known as *“the language triptych”*: Language of learning (basic vocabulary, grammar rules, sentences, language of describing and defining), language for learning (language to communicate, work in groups, asking and answering questions, language to build arguments, language for project work) and language through learning (language and thinking, use of ICT, dictionary skills, using feedback).

In relation to motor skills, Blázquez (1987) indicates that can be classified in defined, semi-defined or not defined. Starting from this classification, defined tasks and semi-defined, based on imitation, are related to the third level of Bloom’s taxonomy (1956) and not defined task, based on problems approach, are related to the sixth level of the same taxonomy.

Forehand (2005) reviews the Bloom's taxonomy (1953) that is concretized in: 1st remember, 2nd understand, 3rd apply, 4th analyze, 5th evaluate and 6th create. Based on this classification, we are going to develop motor skills in relation to cognitive and linguistic competences.

How do we plan our work? The tasks and activities are in relation to the revised Bloom's taxonomy. 1st level, remember, simple games and tasks related to basic physical abilities and warming-up; 2nd level, understand, motor skills related to spatial orientation; 3rd level, apply, motor skills related to simple technical sports gestures; 4th level, analyze, the resolution of simple motor problems through games in small groups, 5th level, evaluate, co-evaluation and peer- assessment activities in small groups and 6th level, create, are modified sports (spaces, number of players, roles, rules...) using reflexive questions to develop interaction and cognitive development. The subject matter contents are closely mapped to second language learning. The dual approach is based on 4Cs framework. "*The propositional movement is based on knowledge...and it meets its purpose*" (Sanchez, 1989:114). Therefore, the aim of CLIL in PE to take part actively in sports is related to use L2 properly.

The contents belong to block number two (Decree 54/2014): *Games and sports*. They are related to basic concepts, technical fundamentals and basic vocabulary of each team sport.

The key competences are the knowledge, abilities and attitudes to acquire the academic and social development. The proposal is related to the following competences: mathematical, linguistic, digital, learning to learn, digital, social and civic, personal initiative and cultural expression.

The assessment criteria are the reference for evaluating and let us make value judgments. They are sequenced by levels. The learning standards are observable tasks that the student performs to master the key competences. A matrix evaluation is created based on rubrics and assessment tools.

The descriptors assess motor skills, linguistic competence and cognitive development. It used the Game Performance Assessment Instrument, known as the acronym GPAI (Oslin et al., 1998), the direct observation, auto-evaluation questionnaires, check lists, rubrics of receptive skills as listening for information and multiple choice test and finally reproductive skills as conversation and spoken expressions. The learning standards are represented by a subject and level code. For example, Bilingual Physical education in 6th grade will be EFB6, the subject content block will be EFB6/2, the number of criteria will be EFB6/2.2 and the number of standard will be EFB6/2.2.1. All of them are related to key competences and assessment tools. We explain a case related to criteria two and four:

- Code EFB6/2.2.1. The contents are games and sports: opposition, cooperation and motor skills. El evaluation criterion is to solve tactical problems of collective games. The standard is: he/she uses expressive resources to solve problems of individual and collective tactic in different situations. The key competences are

LL (learning to learn) CIEE (initiative). The qualification tools used are GPAI questionnaire, check list and class diary.

- Code EFB6/2.4.1./ EFB6/2.4.2./ EFB6/2.4.3. The contents are team sports lexicon in L2, code of fair play and use of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies). El criterion is to know the diversity of motor, playful and sporting activities. The learning standard number 1 is: he/she exposes the differences between team and individual sports using L2, the number 2: he/she recognizes the history and origin of sports and number 3: he/she makes a team sports sheet in L2. The key competences are CL (linguistic) and CSC (social y civic) CD (digital). The qualification tools are direct observation, class diary and verification scale.

The most important methodological principle is the game as an invaluable resource of learning. Scaffoldingⁱⁱⁱ is not less important as a linguistic resource (Vygotsky, 1975). Other important principles are the team work, conflict resolution, the healthy habits, social aspects, cultural contexts and the development of motor skills

CLIL methodology is based on tasks and activities which develop the learning of contents and the communicative use in L2. Richard et, al. (2001) consider Total Physical Response technique (TPR) as a natural teaching technique (Asher, 2000). TPR help us to teach language through motor response of students. We use TPR, learning styles which can be directives like direct command and non-directives like guided discovery and problem- solving (Mosston and Ashworth, 1999).

The blended styles are the key to develop cognitive, affective, social and psychomotor aspects of students. Coral and Lleixá (2013:53) state *“it is better to use a wide range of teaching techniques”*. The non- directive techniques develop better the cognitive processes and complex judgmental. These are related to Higher Order Thinking Skills or HOTS (predicting, hypothesizing, 4th, 5th and 6th levels of Bloom’s taxonomy) and directive techniques develop lower order thinking skills or LOTS (defining, classifying, exemplifying, 1st, 2nd and 3rd levels of Bloom’s taxonomy). Therefore, we will develop the student-centered approach more than teacher-centered approach. Bentley (2011) indicates *“Student-Centered Approach (SCA) improves Student talking Time (STT)”*.

In each Didactic Unit (DU), we have designed a CLIL template (table III) which indicates the aims, key competences, teaching objectives, assessment criteria, indicators, tools, methodological styles, learning outcomes and materials. In each session of the DU we indicate (table IV) teaching objectives, organization, materials, motor skills, linguistic skills, scaffolding and timing. The motor skills are related to linguistic skills based on 4Cs framework, in which scaffolding has an important role.

ⁱⁱⁱ Scaffolding is the provision of temporary, adjustable support (like a builder’s structure) that is provided by a teacher to assist students develop in the learning and teaching process. (Ashman and Conway, 1997) Teacher helps students step by step.

Table I: Contents block related to general objectives and key competences of Primary Education

Physical Education (6th level)															
Block of contents	General Objectives. Primary														Key competences
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	
Block 1. Physical activity and Health	X	X			X			X	X		X				CMCT-CSC-SIEE-LL-CD-CL
Block 2. Perception, abilities and games	X	X	X			X					X		X		CMCT-CSC-SIEE-LL-CD-CL-CE
Block 3. Physical activities-artistic and expressive	X	X			X			X	X		X				CMCT-CSC-SIEE-LL-CD-CL

CMCT (Mathematical), CSC (Social y Civic), SIEE (Initiative), LL (Learning to learn), CD (Digital), CL (Linguistic), CE (Cultural expression)

Table II: Timing. Bilingual Physical Education. 6th grade of Primary Education. Third term

Week	Sessions	Didactic Units And Subject Matter
1	1	Initial Assessment
1-2	5	Traditional games
3-7	15	Team sports
8-9	7	Orienteering games
9	2	Final Assessment

Table III: Didactic Unit 16th "Team sports"

<p>AIMS (Related to P.E General aims A, B, C, F, K, M)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To participate actively in sport activities. - To respect rules in different sports. - To develop basic skills in a second language.
<p>Competences (Related to key competences CMCT, CSC, SIEE, AA, CD, CL, CE)</p>
<p>Teaching Objectives (What I plan to teach)</p> <p>Content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation and opposition strategies in team sports. - Initiation to the team sports. <p>Cognition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Know vocabulary and basic rules of sports in L2 - Enable students to discuss solutions in team sports in L2 <p>Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perspectives on sports. - Encourage students' curiosity in sports tactic. <p>Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language of learning. Key vocabulary: defender, offender, attacker, strike, kick off, home run, - Language for learning. Comparing and contrasting. Make connections and answer: What do you Know about this sport? Which are the main of this sport? How can we design a tactic? Can you write a concept map?

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Language through learning. Predict possible solutions to different problems. Teacher's feedback. Use of new technologies (tablet, computer, digital white board)	
Assessment Criteria (Related to general assessment 2 nd , 3 rd , 4 th , 5 th , 7 th and 8 th)	
Indicators - To be able to participate in sports. - To be able to enjoy doing sports. - To be able to develop language skills in L2.	Tools - Teacher's diary. Systematic observation. Rubric. Control list. GPAI scale.
Methodology (Styles) - Guided discovery. Direct teaching. TPR (Total Physical Respond).	Materials - Computer, projector, digital whiteboard, netbooks and team sports' materials.
Learning Outcomes (What students will be able to do by the end of the didactic unit) - Students will be able to overcome doing sports. - Students will be able to know basic vocabulary of each sport in L2	

Table IV: Session's template

Bilingual Physical Education. Didactic Unit 16TH (1st Session)			
Grade: 6 th Primary Education. Didactic Unit: Team Sports (3 rd Term) Teaching Objectives: 1. To be able to know key rules of mini-football, 2. To be able to pass the ball correctly 3. To be able to improve English level, 4. To be able to respect the rules.		Organization. Individual, work in pairs, small group and whole group. Material: IDB, balls number 5, cones, court, notebook, pen and pencil.	
Motors Skills	Linguistic Skills	Scaffolding	Timing (60')
1. Warming Up 1.1 The teacher shows the students some image flashcards about football. 1.2 The teacher asks the students: What football words do you know in English? They write specific vocabulary on their notebooks, such as defender, offender, goal-keeper, fault, direct free kick, corner, kick, kickoff, forward, penalty, full-time, half-time, score, goal, header, throw in, pass the ball.	Listening, reading, speaking and writing.	Specific words, flashcards, rephrasing and feedback.	(15')
2. Development 2.1 Pass the ball in pairs Flashcard 1 st A 2.2 Pass the ball in small groups. Flashcard 1 st B 2.3 "Pig in the middle". Groups of ten (1 or 2 in the middle). Flashcard 2 nd 2.4. Pass the ball. The students make a rectangle.	Listening, speaking and reading	Flashcards, teacher's demonstration, recasting, gently corrections and	(35')
			5'
			5'
			10'

They have to pass the ball and change places. Groups of five and a ball in each group. Flashcard 3 rd		continuous feedback.	15'
3. Follow Up/ Cool Down 3.1 Stretching in a circle. Whole group. 3.2 Time-line used at the end (as a visual support and scaffold) for organizing information.	Listening, speaking, reading	Enhance motivation and improving mental skills.	(10')
			10'

Table V: Flashcards

Image flashcard 1st A: Passing the ball

Image flashcard 1st B

Image flashcard 2nd: Pig-in-the-middle

Image flashcard 3rd: Pass the ball and change places

3. Discussion and Conclusions

CLIL has an incredible potential for language and content learning. Nowadays, the positive effects of CLIL methodology in non-linguistic disciplines are demonstrated (Alonso, et al., 2015; Coral and Lleixa, 2013; Coyle, et al., 2010). We have found some proposal in Bilingual Physical Education (Alonso, et al., 2015; Chiva-Bartoll, et al., 2015; García Jiménez, et al., 2012, García-Calvo, 2015, García-Calvo and Salaberri, 2018; González-Villora et al., 2013 and Montávez, 2002).

The article shows a Didactic Unit of Bilingual Physical Education aimed at 6th grade of Primary Education. The timing is in the third academic quarter and consists of thirteen sessions. A session's template is presented in detail (table IV).

The Didactic Unit is designed to be implemented during the academic year 2016-2017. Subsequently, it has been put in practice in two different groups and schools at the same time. Therefore, a process of critical reflection has been carried out to improve the learning and teaching processes. We summarize our findings with statements by specialists in the matter.

It is not really easy, but we totally agree with Rottmann (2006:213) *“ideally, it should be a fusion of learning the foreign language through movement and learning the movement through the foreign language at the same time”*. The use of games linked to second learning acquisition increase motivation of the student. (Ramos and Ruiz Omeñaca, 2010).

We must respect the logical progression of contents, objectives and tasks in L2. *“Good scaffolding helps student express himself from the beginning”* (Coral and Lleixá, 2013). García-Calvo, (2015:15) write that *“the daily routines help me to convey input preparing scaffolding (breaking the task down into steps)”*.

In PE in CLIL, we have several pathways of information, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic-tactile and teacher's demonstrations. *“I usually build redundancy*

into the CLIL classroom, animating language use, using language and speech appropriate for students' English level" (García-Calvo, 2015:21).

Errors are a vital part of the learning process. The treatment of the error and recognition of achievement reduce anxiety and frustration of students. When we correct we try to help students to make the meaning clearer. *"Thinking all the ways we can handle errors when the students are speaking... rephrasing is less threatening than direct correction"* (Slattery and Willis, 2001:120-134).

Flexible grouping avoids sport prejudgments and students' integration is facilitated. *"It is important to break social topics. There are not girls sports and there are not boys sports... we must break sexist stereotypes"* (Chiva-Bartoll, 2015:114).

The curriculum design and development will be enriched if the teacher knows several variables: context, sex, age, race, sport ability, linguistic level of proficiency... Gutierrez et al., (2013) state that if we bear in mind several variables, the teacher will develop real and effective solutions.

Motivation and positive reinforcement is the key in Bilingual Physical Education. Slattery and Willis (2001) show some techniques for effective use of English in the classroom, such as common words, patterns, clues, prompts, elicit, rephrasing (what teacher says in as many ways as he/she can) and recasting (repeating in English what students say in mother tongue).

"I usually divide complex tasks or games into two or three simpler, progressive sequences in order to facilitate comprehension...long explanations lacking movement will be avoided" (García-Calvo, 2015:41). In PE in CLIL, linguistic comprehension and mechanisms of perception, decision and execution will improve. Sánchez (1989:110) states that *"The distribution of motor tasks in a progressive way according to their degree of complexity is a didactic requirement... in Physical Education"*. The teacher has to provide scaffolding, support, strategies and tools in the learning and teaching process.

On one hand, PE in CLIL has to bear in mind the subject matter and English language. Coyle, Hood and Marsh (2010:114) state that *"content should always be the dominant element in terms of objectives"*. On the other hand, it is important to take care of the interferences produced in the process.

The teacher must use continuous feedback, because the feedback provides a comprehensible input and output. El input is a key element in second language acquisition and it not necessary to be grammatically sequenced. "Krashen's input hypothesis" shows us that we acquire the target language when we understand language. In this line, Krashen (1985) states that comprehensible input is the only true way a student has to acquire a second language and input will influence the output. Therefore, Magdaleno (2011) writes that Bilingual Physical Education provides excellent resources to acquire a second language, since the students learn in real context. In this Didactic Unit, we have taken into account several factors: linguistic, metalinguistic, contextual, socials, individuals, legislatives and student's proficiency level. A proposal has been develop to improve the educative quality and it serves as a stimulus for future curricular designs on CLIL in PE.

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